

ANALYTICAL REVIEW OF METHODS AND DEVICES FOR MONITORING INTERMEDIATE SPAN OF OVERHEAD POWER LINE.

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Annotation. At present, 90 overhead power lines are not equipped with monitoring systems, therefore, meteorological impacts are monitored visually by mobile teams of network area services, and the received indicative information is transmitted using available means of communication. In accordance with this method, the observer evaluates: the diameter of the ice sleeve, the distribution of deposits over the spans of overhead lines, the type of deposits, the direction and speed of the wind.

Key words: overhead power lines, monitoring, ice methods and devices for icing control, overhead lines, reinsurance and proactive.

From the theory of mechanical strength of an overhead line structure, it is known that destruction occurs when the external force acting on a structural element exceeds the strength limit of this element. When exposed to ice-wind loads on wires and ground wires, the external force is the total force due to the weight of the deposits and the constant (laminar) wind flow - the static component of the load; and due to the presence of deposits of a certain shape and wind of a certain speed and direction - the dynamic component of the load or the dance of the wire (lightning cable).

Because of this, with a scientifically based forecast of the force (destructive) impact of deposits and wind on an overhead line, it is necessary, at least, to measure the weight of deposits, the strength and direction of the wind. Using the visual method, only the volume of deposits is estimated from the approximate diameters of the frost sleeves. It is this approach that causes such a large number of unreasonable swimming trunks, because the specific gravity of deposits, depending on the conditions of their formation, differs by 6–8 times, and, therefore, with the same volume of deposits, their force effect on the overhead line will also differ by 6–8 times.

An increase in errors is also caused by the fact that the volume is estimated from the difference between the diameter of the wire and the deposits on it (a model of deposits in the form of a hollow cylinder), despite the fact that deposits cannot actually be cylindrical and always have a complex irregular shape. In addition, the adopted assessment method does not take into account the uneven thickness of the sediment layer along the length of the span. [1,2]

Thus, the main disadvantages of the visual method include the following: firstly, the fact that the accuracy of the method due to visual assessment (“by eye”) is fundamentally low; secondly, it requires the direct presence of an observer at the place of control, which, in winter off-road conditions, short daylight hours, and inaccessibility of most line sections, greatly complicates the prediction of the type of deposits on the wire, based on solving the multidimensional problem of the thermodynamic exchange process; thirdly, it is practically unrealizable in conditions of poor visibility.

Analyzing all the information known so far about instrumental parametric methods and devices for monitoring ice-wind loads on wires and ground wires of an overhead line, it can be systematized according to the main methods for detecting deposits based on measurements.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The most developed and practically used gravitational method for detecting and measuring deposits on the wire of the intermediate span, implemented by measuring the ice and ice-wind loads on the wire, followed by comparison of the measured values with predetermined values of threshold loads (significant ice and ice-wind, dangerous, allowable loads).

A device for measuring separately ice and wind loads is known, based on the calculation of ice and wind loads from the measured values of ice-wind load and the angle of deviation of a string of insulators with a wire under the action of wind using transformer sensors. The main disadvantage of such a device is that it does not automatically detect the appearance of deposits on the wire, because it does not have a threshold (comparing) element and there is no threshold generator (setting element). In addition, this device fundamentally does not work in the absence of a load current in the phase wire, as well as in the case of melting deposits on the wires with direct current, because the electromotive force in the transformer appears in the presence of an alternating magnetic field caused by an alternating current.[3].

Figure 1. Power line wire capacity monitoring system.

Known more advanced in terms of the principle of operation and design of the device for telemetry of ice load on the wires of the intermediate span of overhead lines [3], which can be used on multi-circuit overhead lines with any type of supports. The device contains a teletransmission channel, a commutator and two spring weight sensors with contact groups of the weight setting on the movable axis of the sensor, on which the wire is suspended. Each sensor is movably suspended

between the traverse of the support and the upper end of the corresponding insulator string, the lower ends of both insulator strings are pivotally connected to each other, forming a V-shaped wire suspension.

Figure 2. Structure of the measuring unit and monitoring center.

This detector gives a signal of the presence of deposits when a certain weight of deposits on the wire is reached, by closing a group of contacts at the moment the wire passes the low point when the wire oscillates under the influence of wind in the plane perpendicular to the line of sight of the span. The defining disadvantage of such a device is that in a strong uniform wind it may never give a deposit detection signal at all, because. will always be in a deflected (non-vertical) position and the contact groups will not be closed. In addition, even with a low specific gravity of deposits, the group of contacts will not close and, therefore, a signal for detecting deposits will not be issued, i.e. will skip the presence of deposits on the wire. With a small weight setting in the sensors, the growth of the false alarm probability will outpace the growth of the probability of correct detection, since any occasional signal exceeding the threshold unrelated to sedimentation (due to variable wind) will trigger a detection signal. Therefore, the considered device has a low probability of correctly detecting deposits of all possible types. [2]

III. CONCLUSION.

The reason for the insecurity of overhead lines from ice-wind accidents primarily lies in the lack of an effective information-measuring system for monitoring overhead lines. Until now, in known works, monitoring systems are not considered as a means of detecting the impact and recognizing its type, recognizing the type of deposits. The problem of dividing the ice-wind load into ice and wind loads has been little studied. Known studies of the impact of dynamic loads of wire dancing are not enough to develop methods and devices for detecting dancing, which is the main cause of overhead lines accidents.

To assess, control and predict the state of the overhead line, and make a decision about the presence of a risk of an accident on the overhead line, it is sufficient to have information about the current state of each of the intermediate spans of the overhead line. At the same time, it is advisable to use monitoring systems only on those intermediate spans on which, according to operating experience, all other things being equal, meteorological effects appear earlier and grow more rapidly than on the other spans of the controlled line.

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